

Stoichiometry controlled syntheses of cyanide-bound iron(II) and iron(III) complexes and their X-ray crystal structures

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Abstract : Two new meridionally positioned tricyanide building blocks consisting of low-spin iron(III), $[(\text{NBu}_4)[\text{Fe}(\text{pzcq})(\text{CN})_3] \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1), and low-spin iron(II), $[\text{PPh}_4]_2[\text{Fe}(\text{pzcq})(\text{CN})_3] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2) [Hpzcq = 8-(pyrazine-2-carboxamido)quinoline], reported. X-Ray crystal structures reveal that, in both the complexes, Fe center is comprised of three C atoms from CN^- ligands and three N atoms from the tridentate pzcq ligand in meridional fashion. It is worth noting that by simple variation of stoichiometric amounts of KCN both of the complexes could be produced from the same starting material. KCN not only binds to the metal center but also able to reduce iron(III) to iron(II) in 2.

Keywords : Cyanide-containing building blocks, role of KCN, X-ray crystal structures, IR spectroscopy.

Introduction

Much research effort has been devoted to the field of cyanide-based materials mainly due to the diverse ranges of topologically unique structures, optical, and magnetic properties¹. Some of them exhibit high temperature magnetic order², photoresponsive properties³, spin-crossover (SCO)⁴, chirality⁵, single-molecule magnet⁶ (SMM) and single chain magnet⁷ (SCM) behaviors. The most common examples include hexacyanidometalates, $[\text{M}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ ($\text{M} = \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}, \text{Cr}^{\text{III}}, \text{Mn}^{\text{III}}$, etc.), which in the presence of reactive metal complexes form robust $\text{M}-(\mu\text{-CN})-\text{M}'$ linkages. In the absence of blocking ligands (e.g. hydrated M^{n+} ions) a well-known family of bimetallic prussian blue analogues are the most commonly encountered structural archetype^{3,8}. However, difficulty in the structural studies of these insoluble materials limits to magneto-structural correlation with these materials. To expand the rich magnetic properties and to better understand the magneto-structural relationship, a typically employed strategy utilizes multidentate ligands to restrict the numbers of $\text{M}-(\mu\text{-CN})-\text{M}'$ units formed during the course of the self-assembly process. A careful choice of the building units and ancillary ligands allow for the engineering of discrete and well-defined complexes (including high nuclearity clusters) in addition to a diverse assortment of

1-D, 2-D and 3-D cyanidometalate materials. Many of them display long-range magnetic order above room temperature, photoresponsive property, and slow relaxation of the magnetization (SCMs) as well^{3,6,7,9}.

The latest strategy is to use of versatile building blocks of general formula $[\text{FeL}(\text{CN})_x]^-$ ($\text{L} =$ a polydentate ligand; $x = 2-4$) that led to numerous new cyanido-bridged low dimensional heterometallic systems with interesting magnetic properties¹⁰. The introduction of well-designed blocking ligands for the cyanide precursors plays a crucial role as it can control the nuclearity, topology, and the dimensionality of resulting materials. Among this large family, several facially and meridionally coordinated tricyanido-ferrate(III) complexes have led to a large number of cyanido-bridged bimetallic complexes containing $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\mu\text{-CN})\text{M}^{\text{II}}$ units¹¹⁻¹⁶.

Our continuing interest in the field of cyanide-based materials led us to develop new cyanide-bound building units¹⁷. In this endeavor, I report syntheses and structural characterizations of tricyanido-iron(III) and iron(II) complexes, and role of KCN is critically discussed.

Experimental

Materials and physical measurements :

8-(Pyrazine-2-carboxamido)quinoline (Hpzcq) and

Fe(pzqc)Cl₂.H₂O were synthesized according to the literature methods¹⁸. All the chemicals used in this study were obtained from E. Merck of GR grade or equivalent quality.

Elemental analyses for C, H and N were performed by the Pregl-Dumas technique on a Thermo Fischer Flash EA1112 analyzer. FT-IR spectra of the complexes were recorded in the range of 400–4000 cm⁻¹ on a Nicolet 750 Magna-IR spectrometer using KBr pellets. The magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature using an EG and G PAR-155 vibrating sample magnetometer, using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as reference material; diamagnetic correction was made by Pascal's constants for all the constituent atoms.

Synthesis of complex [(NBu₄)[Fe(pzqc)(CN)₃]·1.5H₂O (1) : To a suspension of Fe(pzqc)Cl₂.H₂O (1.97 g, 5 mmol) in 60 ml of methanol, added KCN (0.97 g, 15 mmol). The mixture was refluxed for 12 h, resulting as a dark brown solution which was concentrated via rotary evaporation to ca. 20 ml volume. To this added aqueous solution (30 ml) of tetrabutylammonium bromide (1.61 g, 5 mmol) with stirring. The resulting solution then filtered which on standing at room temperature, greenish brown crystalline materials separated from the solution. The product was isolated by filtration, washed with water and air dried. Yield : 2.45 g, 76%. Anal. Calcd. C₃₃H₄₇FeN₈O_{2.5} : C, 60.78; H, 7.21; N, 17.19. Found : C, 60.70; H, 7.30; N, 17.02. Crops of greenish-brown block-shaped crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction were obtained from slow evaporation of methanol solution after few days. IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3444 br (ν_{NH}, OH), 1671 m (ν_{C=O}), 2111, 2123 m (ν_{C≡N}); μ_{eff} 1.91 B.M.

Synthesis of complex [PPh₄]₂[Fe(pzqc)(CN)₃]·6H₂O (2) : To a suspension of Fe(pzqc)Cl₂.H₂O (1.97 g, 5 mmol) in 60 ml of methanol, added KCN (1.95 g, 30 mmol). The mixture was refluxed for 12 h, resulting as a dark violet solution which was concentrated via rotary evaporation to ca. 20 ml volume. To this added aqueous solution (30 ml) of PPh₄Br (4.20 g, 10 mmol) with stirring. The resulting solution then filtered which on standing at room temperature, violet crystalline materials separated from the solution. The product was isolated by filtration, washed with water and air dried. Dark-violet single crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction were obtained from slow evapo-

ration of 1 : 1 solvent mixture of methanol-water within one week. Yield : 5.10 g, 87%. Anal. Calcd. C₆₅H₅₇FeN₇O₇P₂ : C, 66.89; H, 4.88; N, 8.40. Found : C, 66.80; H, 4.80; N, 8.28; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3447 br (ν_{NH}, OH), 1662 m (ν_{C=O}), 2022, 2051 m (ν_{C≡N}); μ_{eff} 0.02 B.M.

X-Ray crystallography :

Intensity data for complexes **1** and **2** were collected at low temperature with a Nonius Kappa CCD diffractometer using Graphite-monochromated Mo/Kα radiation (λ = 0.71073 Å). Cell refinement, indexing and scaling of the data sets were performed using programs DENZO-SMN and SCALEPACK¹⁹. The structures were analyzed by direct method and refined by the full-matrix least-square technique based on F² using SHELXL97²⁰ programs with all the reflections. Thermal parameters for all the non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. All the hydrogen atoms bound to carbon were placed in calculated positions using a riding model while those attached to lattice water were located in the difference Fourier map and refined using fixed isotropic thermal parameters based on their respective parent atoms. All the calculations were performed using the WinGX System, Ver. 1.70.01²¹. The crystal parameters and basic information relating to data collections and structure refinements for all the compounds are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Crystal data and structure refinement for complexes **1** and **2**

Compound	1	2
Empirical formula	C ₃₃ H ₄₇ FeN ₈ O _{2.5}	C ₆₅ H ₅₇ FeN ₇ O ₇ P ₂
Formula weight	651.64	1165.97
Temperature (K)	150(2)	150(2)
Wavelength (Å)	0.71073	0.71073
Crystal system	Monoclinic	Monoclinic
Space group	P2 ₁ /n	P2 ₁ /c
Unit cell dimensions :		
<i>a</i> (Å)	13.690(4)	16.6816(7)
<i>b</i> (Å)	14.896(4)	9.1623(4)
<i>c</i> (Å)	17.373(5)	39.0459(10)
α (°)	90	90
β (°)	100.696(5)	95.245(10)
γ (°)	90	90
Volume (Å ³)	3481(2)	5942.9(4)
Z	4	4
D _{calc} (g cm ⁻³)	1.243	1.303

Table-1 (contd.)

Absorption coefficient (mm ⁻¹)	0.475	0.367
<i>F</i> (000)	1388	2432
θ Range for data collection (°)	3.49–27.91	2.28–27.94
Limiting indices	-17 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 17, -17 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 19, -22 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 22	-21 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 21, -12 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 11, -51 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 51
Reflections collected	14993/	34301/13608
Independent reflection/ <i>R</i> _{int}	8216/0.1216	8201/0.0705
Data/restraints/parameters	3098/4/422	8201/7/838
Goodness-of-fit on <i>F</i> ²	0.918	1.043
Final <i>R</i> indices [<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>)]	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0646, w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.1094	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0775, w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.1899
<i>R</i> indices (all data)	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.2231, w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.1525	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.1388, w <i>R</i> 2 = 0.2266

Results and discussion

Syntheses and general characterizations :

Treatment of 1 : 3 molar ratio of Fe(pzqc)Cl₂·H₂O and KCN readily afforded **1**, while use of the excess KCN resulted **2** in high yield (Scheme 1). The presence of excess KCN acts as reducing agent for the reduction of iron(III) center which ultimately produced complex **2**. The corresponding tetrabutylammonium derivative (**1**) was easily prepared via addition of an aqueous [NBu₄]Br to

Elemental analysis and TLC measurements confirm the purity of the complexes as only one spot was observed for each complex. The molar conductance values indicate that complex **1** exhibits 1 : 1 electrolytic nature whereas complex **2** exhibits 1 : 2 electrolytic nature in methanol solvent. Room temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements demonstrate that compound **2** is diamagnetic while complex **1** is paramagnetic. The above studies conclude that the oxidation state of iron in complex **1** is +3 whereas it is +2 in complex **2**. The infrared spectra of **1** and **2** display cyano stretching absorptions that are characteristic of those observed for related complexes^{11–18}. For example, the high-energy ν_{CN} absorptions (2111, 2123 cm⁻¹) seen in **1** indicate that the iron centers are trivalent and are in the range reported for a variety of tricyanometalates^{11–18}. Similar stretching frequencies were found for compound **2** in relatively lower energy region (2022, 2051 cm⁻¹) and consistent with the divalent state of the central metal ion.

Description of the crystal structures :

Compound **1** crystallizes in the monoclinic P2₁/n space group and consists of [Fe(pzqc)(CN)₃]⁻ anion, tetrabutylammonium cation, and crystallization solvent water molecules. For the complex anion, the tridentate N-donor ligand (pzqc) coordinates the iron(III) center in a

Scheme 1. Routes to the syntheses of complexes **1** and **2**.

the crude reaction mixture, while complex **2** was precipitated as tetraphenylphosphonium salt. Both complexes **1** and **2** are soluble in most common polar organic solvents (e.g. MeCN, MeOH, CH₂Cl₂ and DMF) presenting themselves as promising building units for the construction of multinuclear complexes.

meridional fashion and the three cyanide groups occupy the remaining meridional position (Fig. 1). The distances between the iron(III) and the nitrogen of the pzqc and the carbon of cyanide ligands vary in the range of 1.871(3)–1.974(5) Å and (1.933(4)–1.956(5) Å) (Table 2), respectively, which are in good agreement to those reported for

Fig. 1. Molecular structure of **1** showing the selected atom numbering scheme. Ellipsoids are drawn with 30% probability. The hydrogen atoms and solvent molecules are omitted for clarity.

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (Å) and bond angles (°) for complexes **1** and **2**

1				2			
Fe1–N1	1.974(3)	Fe1–C15	1.956(4)	Fe1–N1	1.979(4)	Fe1–C15	1.949(4)
Fe1–N2	1.871(3)	Fe1–C16	1.933(5)	Fe1–N2	1.945(3)	Fe1–C16	1.894(5)
Fe1–N4	1.946(4)	Fe1–C17	1.954(4)	Fe1–N4	1.921(4)	Fe1–C17	1.941(4)
N5–C15–Fe1	177.4(4)	N6–C16–Fe1	177.2(4)	N5–C15–Fe1	176.8(4)	N6–C16–Fe1	178.9(6)
N7–C17–Fe1	178.7(4)			N7–C17–Fe1	177.2(5)		

other cyano-containing mononuclear iron(III) low-spin complexes^{11–18}. The Fe–N(amide) distance (1.871 Å) is significantly shorter than the other two Fe–N lengths (1.946–1.974 Å) associated with pzcq ligand, which may be due to the presence of a strong σ -donor effect of the deprotonated amide nitrogen. The iron(III) ion has distorted octahedral coordination geometry mainly due to the stereo requirement of the pzcq ligand as indicated by the shorter bite angle of 83.1(1)°. However, the cyanides are almost linear and they vary in the range 177.2(4)–178.7(4)°. The uncoordinated nitrogen on pyrazine rings of the ligand and the nitrogen from the cyanides interact with the lattice water molecules through the hydrogen bonds to form an extensive network (Fig. 2). The crystal packing is further stabilized by the involvement of face-to-face π – π stacking interactions (3.727 Å) between aromatic rings of two adjacent pzcq ligands (Fig. 2).

The crystal structure of **2** consists of *mer*-[Fe(pzcq)(CN)₃]²⁻ anion (Fig. 3), uncoordinated

tetraphenylphosphonium cations, and lattice water molecules. The structure of complex anion **2** is very similar to compound **1** in that the iron atom has a slightly distorted octahedral geometry, comprising of meridionally positioned three C atoms from CN⁻ ligands and three N atoms from the tridentate pzcq ligand. The Fe–N(pzcq) and Fe–C(cyano) bond distances vary in the range 1.921(4)–1.979(4) and 1.894(5)–1.949(4) Å, respectively, values of which are very similar to those found in complex **1**. However, the bond distance is not a proper diagnostic parameter for the recognition of oxidation state of iron as both of them have similar bond distances especially in strong ligand field environments. Features together with the presence of two tetraphenylphosphonium cations in the structure of **2**, the diamagnetic nature of the complex, and the relatively lower values of cyanide stretching frequencies clearly demonstrate the low-spin character of iron(II) in **2**. The cyanides are essentially linear as reflected from their bond angles (176.8(4)–

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Fig. 2. Crystal structure of **2** showing the selected atom numbering scheme. Ellipsoids are presented with 30% probability. The hydrogen atoms and solvent molecules are omitted for clarity.

Fig. 3. Molecular packing of complex **1** showing $\pi \cdots \pi$ stacking and hydrogen bonding schemes.

Fig. 4. A part of the molecular packing of **2** showing helical water clusters propagating along the *b* axis.

178.9(6)°). In the crystal packing, the PPh_4^+ cations are grouped by pairs exhibiting the CH- π interaction pattern with a P-P separation of 6.860 Å. Most importantly, the lattice water molecules form a well defined helical water clusters along the crystallographic *b* axis as depicted in Fig. 4.

Conclusion

Meridionally positioned tricyanide building blocks consisting of low-spin iron(III) (**1**) and low-spin iron(II) (**2**) centers are synthesized and X-ray crystallographically characterized. It is interesting to note that by simple variation of stoichiometric amounts of KCN both of them can be produced from the same starting materials. The role of the excess KCN is noteworthy as it not only binds to the metal center but also able to reduce iron(III) to iron(II). These cyanide bound Fe-complexes could be excellent starting material for the construction of polynuclear magnetic materials.

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Supplementary data

CCDC 892465 and 892466 contain the supplementary crystallographic data for **1** and **2**, respectively. These data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>, or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : (+44) 1223-336-033; or *E-mail* : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

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